

Ethics in S&P Research Pre-Screening Survey

We are a research team from [University]. We are studying how security and privacy (S&P) researchers assess and consider ethical implications of their research. We would like to invite you to a 60 minute interview to discuss considerations of ethics during your research process and within the security and privacy research community. To participate in the interview, we ask you to answer a few questions related to your experience and role in the S&P research field. The questionnaire should take at most 10 minutes.

At the end of the survey, we ask for your email address to contact you, we will not use the e-mail address for any other purposes and delete it when we no longer need it.

We thank you for your time!

General Questions

We would like to know some general information about you and your role in the security and privacy S&P research community.

[Q1] What is your role / job description? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- (Co-)Author (of research papers)
- Program Committee/ Reviewer member at any of the following conferences "IEEE S&P, CCS, USENIX, NDSS, big four" PETS, CSCW, CHI
- Institutional Review Board / Ethics Review Board / Ethics committee member (spell out)
- Other:

We want to know what role you fulfill in the S&P research community.

[Q2] How many years of experience do you have in S&P research?

Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

[Q3] What is your current job title? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Professor
- PhD student
- Student
- Postdoc
- Ethics Committee member
- Research assistant
- prefer not to disclose
- Other:

[Q4] What is your gender? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- woman
- man
- non-binary
- prefer not to disclose
- Prefer to self-describe: [text]

[Q5] Where do you currently work?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Europe
- North America
- South America
- Asia
- Africa
- Oceania

Author specific questions

If you are not an author of a research paper in Security and Privacy research, you may skip these questions.

[Q1] How many (published) papers have you (co-)authored?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0-2
- 2-5
- 6-10
- 10-20
- 20+
- Other

[Q2] Have you encountered ethical issues during your research process?

If you feel comfortable sharing please describe the situation and the ethical issues that you encountered.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- not sure

Make a comment on your choice here:

Reviewer Specific questions

If you have never reviewed papers for a conference, you may skip these questions.

[Q1] How many papers have you reviewed?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0-2
- 2-5
- 6-10
- 10-20
- 20+

[Q2] Have you flagged a paper due to ethical concerns?

If you feel comfortable sharing please describe the situation and the ethical issues that you encountered.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- not sure

Make a comment on your choice here:

IRB specific questions

If you are not on an IRB / Ethics Board you may skip these questions.

[Q1] How long have you been on an IRB / Ethics review board?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0-1 years
- 1-3 years
- 3-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-20 years
- 20+ years

[Q2] Have you ever flagged a paper due to ethical concerns?

If you feel comfortable sharing please describe the situation and the ethical issues that you encountered.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- not sure

Make a comment on your choice here:

Contact Information and interview scheduling

Please let us know if you are interested in participating in the study and how to contact you.

[Q1] Are you interested in participating in a study about ethics in Security & Privacy research?

If you select no you will not be contacted.*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no

[Q3] Please enter the email address you want to be contacted on, so we can contact you to schedule an interview. *

(This question was asked only if they said yes to being contacted)

Please write your answer here:

[Q4] If you want to share you can enter your timezone/city below. If you share this information we can take it into account when scheduling the interviews.

Please write your answer here:

Thank you for answering the questions! If you are interested in participating in the study we will contact you.

Thank you for completing this survey.